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Evaluation of the relevant mass and heat transfer phenomena in a packed bed membrane reactor for the direct conversion of CO₂ to dimethyl ether

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relevant heat and mass transfer phenomena occurring at the different scales in a packed bed (membrane) reactor for the direct conversion of CO₂ to dimethyl ether (DME) via the implementation of 2D heterogeneous reactor models. Intra-particle diffusion limitations were found to be relevant for particle diameters larger than 1 mm and temperature above 220 °C, such that the catalyst efficiency drops down to 50% and 5% for the Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ and the HZSM-5, respectively, in the most critical conditions (i.e., 270 °C and D_p of 10 mm). A component-specific Thiele modulus-efficiency correlation was developed based on the results of the rigorous particle model to account for pore-diffusion limitations without having to solve a complex heterogeneous reactor model. This correlation shows the typical behavior reported in literature for power law kinetics and accurately predicts the reaction performance with deviation of less than 5% for values of the Thiele modulus lower than 2. In the packed bed membrane reactor (PBMR), the concentration polarization (CP) also showed to affect the reactor performance. The concentration of water at the surface of the membrane selective layer was found to be up to 64% lower than the concentration in the bulk phase, hindering the effectiveness of the membrane separation. To account for this phenomenon via a simplified approach, a Sherwood-type correlation was developed to determine a CP mass transfer coefficient, based on the results obtained via the rigorous 2D PBMR model. Such correlation showed to predict with high accuracy (i.e., errors lower than 5%) the effect of the CP on the PBMR performance. Differently from the pore diffusion and CP phenomena, the intra-particle heat transfer, the particle–fluid mass and heat transfer as well as the axial dispersion were found to have a negligible effect on the reactor behavior. Finally, given the relevant mass/heat transfer phenomena, this study proposes further reactor optimization strategies, such as the reduction of the zeolite loading in the bifunctional catalyst bed by ca. 90% with respect to what is reported in literature.

1. Introduction

The carbon capture and utilization (CCU) technology has been identified as one of the most attractive long-term solution for the mitigation of climate change. Besides the direct (physical) CO₂ utilization pathways, processing (i.e., via chemical transformation) the captured CO₂ to obtain more valuable products, would also allow to synthesize carbon-based products (e.g., methane, methanol, olefins), reducing our dependency on fossil fuels [1–4]. In this scenario, the synthesis of dimethyl ether (DME) is particularly attractive. DME has been identified as a high-efficiency compression ignition fuel, due to its autoignition properties, high cetane number (i.e., 60), low boiling point (i.e., –24.8 °C), and the lack of C-C bonds [5–8]. Furthermore, with a properly

designed injection system, NO_x emissions can achieve ultra-low emission vehicle (ULEV) limits [9]. All these features make DME an attractive alternative to diesel as transportation fuel, requiring any (or limited) changes in the existing engines [5,10].

Currently, DME is synthesized from syngas via two approaches: 1) the indirect route, where methanol is first synthesized and then dehydrated to DME in a second reactor; 2) the direct route, where methanol synthesis and dehydration occur simultaneously in a single reaction unit. The advantage of the indirect route is the possibility to separately optimize the reaction conditions of the two steps, as well as to set two different scales to meet the different market demands of methanol and DME. However, from a thermodynamic point of view, the immediate consumption of methanol to form DME in the direct route is beneficial to achieve higher DME yield, especially when using pure CO₂ feeds [11].

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Nomenclature	
Symbol	description, (unit), reference
P_i	Partial pressure of component i, (bar)
k_j	Kinetic constant of reaction j, (-), See ref. Table S1
b_i	Adsorption constant of component i, (-), See ref. Table S1
K_i	Equilibrium constant of reaction j, (-), See ref. Table S1
ϕ_i	Permeance of component i, ($\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{Pa}^{-1}$), Table S3 and [49]
R_p or D_p	Catalyst particle radius or diameter, (m)
r_j	Reaction rate of reaction j per catalyst mass, ($\text{mol s}^{-1}\text{kg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$), Section S1 (S.I.)
r_i'' or r_j''	Reaction rate of component i or reaction j per catalyst volume, ($\text{mol s}^{-1}\text{m}_{\text{cat}}^{-3}$)
$D_{\text{eff},i}$	Effective diffusivity of component i, (m^2/s), Eq. S.4
λ_{eff}	Effective diffusivity of catalyst, ($\text{W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), Eq. S.6
$k_{i,\text{ext}}$	External (particle–fluid) mass transfer coefficient of component i, ($\text{m}_{\text{react}}^3 \text{m}_{\text{cat}}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), Correlation of Dwlvedi [41] (Eq. S.7-S.9)
h_{ext}	External (particle–fluid) heat transfer coefficient, ($\text{W m}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$), Correlation of Gupta et al. [62] Eq. S.10-S.11
C_i	Concentration of component i, (mol/m^3)
$(-\Delta H_r)$	Heat of reaction, (J/mol), See Introduction
T	Temperature, (K)
N_r and N_s	Number of reaction and of species, (-)
φ_i	Thiele modulus per component i, (-), Eq. 7
η_i	Effectiveness factor per component i, (-), Eq. 8–9 and Eq. 43
$r_{i,\text{obs}}''$	Observed reaction rate of component i per catalyst volume, ($\text{mol s}^{-1}\text{m}_{\text{cat}}^{-3}$), Eq. S.24
ρ_{cat}	Catalyst density (include catalyst porosity), ($\text{kg}_{\text{cat}}/\text{m}_{\text{cat}}^3$), Table S2
A_{cat}	Catalyst particle external area, (m^2)
V_{cat}	Catalyst particle volume, (m^3)
a_{memb}	Membrane area per reactor volume, ($\text{m}_{\text{memb}}^2/\text{m}_{\text{react}}^3$)
a_{heat}	Heat exchange area per reactor volume, ($\text{m}_{\text{react}}^2/\text{m}_{\text{react}}^3$)
Ca	Carberry number, (-), Eq. S.25
U	Global heat transfer coefficient, ($\text{W m}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$), Eq. S.19
$J_{\text{perm},i}$	Permeation flux of, ($\text{mol s}^{-1}\text{m}_{\text{memb}}^{-2}$), Eq. 21
R_i	Reaction rate of component i per reactor volume, ($\text{mol s}^{-1}\text{m}_{\text{react}}^{-3}$), Eq. 19 or Eq. 20
D_{cat}	Catalyst dilution by volume, ($\text{m}_{\text{cat}}^3/\text{m}_{\text{solid}}^3$), Set to 0.66
ϵ_{bed}	Packed bed porosity, ($\text{m}_{\text{void}}^3/\text{m}_{\text{react}}^3$), Set to 0.4
$x_{\text{cat}1}$ and $x_{\text{cat}2}$	Volume fraction of catalyst 1 (CuZA) and catalyst 2 (HZSM-5), ($\text{m}_{\text{cat}1\text{or}2}^3/\text{m}_{\text{cat}}^3$)
ρ_f	Fluid density, (kg/m^3), Peng and Robison EoS [31]
β	Friction factor from Ergun equation, (bar/m), Eq. 24
μ_f	Fluid viscosity, (Pa·s), [31]
M_i	Molecular weight of component i, (kg/mol)
v	Superficial gas velocity, ($\text{m}_{\text{gas}}^3 \text{m}_{\text{react}}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
L_M	Membrane length, (m)
L_R	Reactor length, (m)
D_{ri} or R_{ri}	Reactor inner diameter or radius, (m)
D_{ro} or R_{ro}	Reactor outer diameter or radius, (m)
D_{mi} or R_{mi}	Membrane inner diameter or radius, (m)
D_{mo} (D_M) or R_{mo}	Membrane outer diameter or radius, (m)
$D_{ax,i}$	Axial dispersion coefficient of component i, (m^2/s), Correlation of Gunn [42,52] Eq. S.12-S.15
$D_{rad,i}$	Radial dispersion coefficient of component i, (m^2/s), Correlation of Gunn [42,52] Eq. S.16-S.18
$k_{CP,i}$	Concentration polarization coefficient of component i, ($\text{m}_{\text{react}}^3 \text{m}_{\text{memb}}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), Eq. 33, 44–45
Re	Reynolds number (based on interstitial fluid velocity), (-)
Sc	Schmidt number, (-)
Sh	Sherwood number, (-)
$\langle C_{i,r} \rangle$	Average concentration in the radial direction of the reaction zone, (mol/m^3)
Pe_{ent}	Entrance Peclet number, (-)
X_{CO_2}	CO ₂ conversion, (-), Eq. 35
Y_i	Product yield, (-), Eq. 36
S_i	Product selectivity, (-), Eq. 37
$F_{\text{CO}_2,\text{imb}}$	CO ₂ transmembrane flow, (-), Eq. 38
WR	Water removal efficiency, (-), Eq. 41
T_w	Temperature imposed at reactor wall (i.e., via boiling water), (K)
Subscript or Superscript description	
s	Evaluated at the surface
b	Bulk property
in	Inlet condition
out	Outlet condition
Cat, cat1 and cat2	Catalyst, catalyst 1 (CuZA) and catalyst 2 (HZSM-5)
eq	Equilibrium value
sm	Evaluated at the membrane surface
R or P	Property/condition of Reaction or Permeation zone

When replacing the carbon source (i.e., CO) with pure CO₂, the direct (or one-step) DME synthesis occurs according to the following reaction scheme:

The methanol synthesis takes place both directly via CO₂ hydrogenation (3) and indirectly, via the intermediate formation of CO (2) and its subsequent hydrogenation (1). Reactions 1–3 are typically carried out

over a Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ catalyst [12–14]. The methanol dehydration (3), instead, requires an acid function, typically given by γ -Al₂O₃ or zeolites such as HZSM-5 [15–17]. Thus, the one-step DME synthesis requires a bifunctional catalyst, commonly given by physical mixtures of the metallic and acid functions. However, being CO₂ less reactive than CO and given the large volume of water produced by the reaction system, efforts have been made by different researchers to improve the activity and stability of both the metallic and acid catalysts [11].

The methanol and DME production are both exothermic and thermodynamically limited processes, favored by higher pressures and low temperatures. Besides, all the reactions lead to the production of large volume of water, which poses even stronger thermodynamic limitations and contributes to catalyst deactivation phenomena during long-term operation [18–20]. The production of water as main reaction by-product has been widely recognized as the main challenge of the CO₂ hydrogenation to DME, such that researchers are placing great efforts in two research lines: 1) improvement of the catalyst stability and 2)

proposing novel reactor concepts, integrating reaction, separation and heat integration [21]. Considering the latter category, it is clear that the in-situ removal of water from the reaction environment would enormously improve the reaction performance as well as the catalyst stability [22–27]. Several studies have already proven, mainly from a modeling perspective, that the incorporation of water-selective membranes in conventional reactors is an effective strategy to overcome the thermodynamic limitations and to render the process more attractive [21–23,28–30].

In our previous study, we have developed a 1D phenomenological membrane reactor model to investigate the effect of membrane properties (i.e., permeability and perm-selectivity) on the reaction performance. We proposed and optimized a reactor configuration where a sweep gas stream containing the reactant (CO_2 and H_2) is circulated in co-current mode to promote the selective removal of water from the reaction environment [31]. In a second study, we have further optimized the membrane reactor, proposing the circulation of boiling water in an external jacket as an effective heat management solution. The membrane reactor was then scaled-up and integrated at flowsheet level, to investigate its potential to improve the process efficiency and economics [32].

Our previous studies were based on reactor models developed according to a simplistic approach, where an ideal flow pattern is assumed, combined with a kinetic regime. These hypotheses are valid under certain conditions, which usually verify at laboratory scale [33,34]. When such hypotheses fail, more rigorous reactor models, which include the interplay of multiscale heat and mass transfer phenomena become essential. In the majority of the cases, these models have to deal with multiple phases (i.e., heterogeneous model) and are described by a complex non-linear system of equations [35]. Thus, rigorous reactor modeling requires specifically developed software and is usually computationally expensive, requiring long simulation times and a significantly larger memory allocation space. Therefore, evaluating the relevance of the heat and mass transfer at different reactor scales is crucial to identify the phenomena which affect the reactor behavior and that, as a consequence, must be accounted for. This is even more important when it comes to investigate novel technologies, such as membrane reactors, coupled with relatively complex reaction schemes, such as CO_2 utilization pathways.

In this work, the mass and heat transfer phenomena in a packed bed (membrane) reactor for the direct conversion of CO_2 to dimethyl ether are investigated at different scales. To that end, the work uses a bifunctional catalysts based on the physical mixture of $\text{Cu}/\text{ZnO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and HZSM-5.

A particle model is developed to assess the extent of intra-particle mass and heat transfer limitations in relevant reaction conditions, as well as their impact on the performance of the packed bed reactor, with and without the membrane (i.e., PBR and PBMR, respectively). The choice of the catalyst particle diameter in fixed/packed bed reactors is crucial. Large particles inhibit severe pressure drops, but, at the same time, induce significant internal mass transfer limitations. These limitations are often neglected and not quantified in literature, given the complexity of this reaction system. Indeed, simulation results often led to unrealistic values in terms of catalyst efficiency [36,37]. More recently, Chakib et al. developed a heterogeneous reactor model to study the pore-diffusion limitations involved in the one-step DME synthesis from CO_2 -rich feedstocks, using bifunctional catalyst based on $\text{Cu}/\text{ZnO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ [38]. In this study, it was found that the internal mass transfer limitation are significant for particle diameter larger than 2 mm, while the maximum temperature difference in the particle is never above 1 °C. However, in the aforementioned study, there's no distinction between the methanol synthesis and dehydration catalyst particles. Furthermore, $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is used instead of zeolites. The $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ has usually pores between 5 and 20 nm, while HZSM-5 is known for its microporous structure, as well as for enhancing the DME formation rate [39], which are two features that could render the effect of pore-diffusion even more

limiting.

Very recently, Ateka et al. proposed a macro-kinetic model for the direct synthesis of DME from $\text{CO}_2\text{-CO}$ mixtures over a $\text{CuO-ZnO-ZrO}_2@SAPO\text{-11}$ core-shell catalyst [40]. The model incorporates the impact of intra-particle diffusion restriction by resolving the concentration profile within the core-shell particle. However, this model is only applicable to the specific catalyst configuration and, like many other models within the literature, resolving the concentration profile within the catalyst pellet necessitates an exhaustive heterogeneous model for accounting for internal mass and heat transfer restraints at the reactor scale.

In this work, once identified the relevance of these phenomena using a rigorous modeling approach, we propose and develop a Thiele modulus-efficiency correlation for the calculation of the effective reaction rate via a short-cut method, which does not require to couple reactor and particle model.

Thereafter, we investigate the particle-fluid interphase, to assess the relevance of any external mass or heat transfer limitation, which means the presence of concentration and temperature gradients from the bulk fluid phase to the surface of the catalyst particle (i.e., in the particle boundary layer). In laminar systems, with little mixing or low superficial velocities, these gradients can be significant. However, these phenomena do not add much complexity to the reactor modeling, and can be accounted for using state-of-the-art correlations to define heat and mass transfer coefficients [34,41].

Packed bed (membrane) reactors are usually modeled as plug flow reactors (PFRs), based on the assumption of no mixing in the axial direction. However, in real conditions, mixing can be relevant due to the diffusion, the turbulent flow around the solid particles or to the presence of radial velocity profiles [34]. In this work, we analyze deviations from the ideal plug flow behavior via the implementation of the axial dispersion model, using the axial dispersion coefficient approach [42].

The introduction of the membrane in the packed bed reactor adds more complexity to the transport phenomena. Indeed, concentration gradients can develop in the radial direction giving rise to a phenomenon which in membrane separation is known as concentration polarization (CP). CP occurs when the concentration of a species increases or decreases in the proximity of the membrane surface (i.e., in the boundary layer) due to the species permeation, thus affecting the overall rate of permeation. This phenomenon is analogue to the fluid-particle mass transfer. Thus, different types of correlations based on either Sherwood (Sh) or Peclet (Pe) number have been empirically developed in the past, mostly for gas separation processes (i.e. no reaction and absence of catalytic bed) or for membrane distillation (i.e., water pervaporation) [43–46]. Specific correlations for this system have never been developed and such phenomenon has often been neglected, especially for porous membranes combined with high vapor permeation flux. Nevertheless, Boon et al. [43], proposed obtaining Sh correlation for the mass transfer resistance by utilizing the analogy between heat and mass transfer and finding literature correlations for the Nusselt number in laminar flow. However, in the same study, the authors highlighted the importance of solving 2D model equations to accurately describe the concentration polarization phenomena for high permeable membranes. Indeed, the radial component of the velocity and/or the radial dispersion phenomena resulted in a more accurate prediction of the concentration gradient developing in the proximity of the membrane surface. Furthermore, they found that as the permeation flux increases, the divergence between the 2D model prediction and 1D model incorporating literature Sh correlation for the CP-mass transfer coefficient also increased.

Therefore, in this study we develop a 2D packed bed membrane reactor model to evaluate the relevance of the radial concentration gradients generated by the presence of the membrane. From the simulations results of the 2D model, we developed a Sherwood-type correlation to account for the CP phenomena via a simplified approach. Indeed, the CP mass transfer coefficient allows to correct the driving

force for the permeation flux, without the need to solve 2D equations.

2. Modeling equations and numerical implementation

2.1. Reaction kinetics and membrane properties

The reactions 1–3 are assumed to be carried out over a Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃, following the kinetic of Portha et al. [47], while reaction 4 occurs over a HZSM-5 catalyst, according to the kinetic of Ortega et al. [48]. The reaction rates expressions are reported in Eq. 1–4.

$$r_1 = k_1 b_{CO} \left\{ \frac{P_{CO} P_{H_2}^{3/2} - \frac{P_{CH_3OH}}{P_{H_2}^{1/2} K_1}}{(1 + b_{CO} P_{CO} + b_{CO_2} P_{CO_2}) \left[P_{H_2}^{1/2} + \left(\frac{b_{H_2O}}{b_{H_2}^{1/2}} \right) P_{H_2O} \right]} \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$r_2 = k_2 b_{CO_2} \left\{ \frac{P_{CO_2} P_{H_2} - \frac{P_{CO} P_{H_2O}}{K_2}}{(1 + b_{CO} P_{CO} + b_{CO_2} P_{CO_2}) \left[P_{H_2}^{1/2} + \left(\frac{b_{H_2O}}{b_{H_2}^{1/2}} \right) P_{H_2O} \right]} \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$r_3 = k_3 b_{CO_2} \left\{ \frac{P_{CO_2} P_{H_2}^{3/2} - \frac{P_{CH_3OH} P_{H_2O}}{P_{H_2}^{3/2} K_3}}{(1 + b_{CO} P_{CO} + b_{CO_2} P_{CO_2}) \left[P_{H_2}^{1/2} + \left(\frac{b_{H_2O}}{b_{H_2}^{1/2}} \right) P_{H_2O} \right]} \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$r_4 = k_4 \left\{ \frac{(b_{CH_3OH} P_{CH_3OH})^2 \left[1 - P_{H_2O} P_{DME} / (P_{CH_3OH}^2 K_4) \right]}{\left(1 + b_{CH_3OH} P_{CH_3OH} + b_{H_2O}^* P_{H_2O} \right)^2} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Details on the kinetic model are given in section 1 of supporting information (S.I.). The kinetic model was validated with experimental data obtained with a physical mixture of 50 wt% Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ and 50 wt% HZSM-5 (see S.I., Fig. S1).

The membranes used for the PBMR are alumina supported carbon molecular sieve membranes (Al-CMSM). The permeation properties of these membranes are reported in our previous study [49] and summarized in S.I. (section 2).

2.2. Intra-particle heat and mass transfer phenomena

2.2.1. Particle model

The mass (Eq. 5) and heat (Eq. 6) balances in the catalyst particle are reported in Table 1 with the corresponding boundary conditions. The equations are derived for a spherical particle with a radius R_p . At the center of the particle ($r = 0$), the concentration/temperature gradient is zero, given the symmetry of the system. At the surface of the particle ($r = R_p$), we consider two scenarios: a) for negligible external (i.e., fluid-particle) heat and/or mass transfer limitations, the surface

concentration/temperature equal those in the bulk fluid; and b) when heat and/or mass transfer limitations exist, the mass/heat flux across the particle outer surface equals the mass/transfer flux across the boundary layer (see section 2.3).

2.2.2. Adapted Thiele modulus and effectiveness factor

Alternatively to the above particle model to account for pore-diffusion limitations, a simplified short-cut approach based on the Thiele modulus would increase the efficiency of the computation significantly. However, none of the state-of-the-art short-cut methods are applicable to this system (i.e., a complex network including multi-component and equilibrium reactions). We propose here an adapted Thiele modulus approach to estimate the catalyst efficiency from information on the catalyst geometry and bulk properties.

We define the component-specific Thiele modulus (φ_i) and the corresponding effectiveness factor (η_i) as reported in Eq. 7 and 8, respectively. The Thiele modulus compares the maximum reaction rate ($r_{i,s}''$) with the maximum diffusion rate, which is proportional to the difference $C_{i,s} - C_{i,eq}$ for a reversible reaction. The effectiveness factor is based on the observed or actual reaction rate ($r_{i,obs}''$), defined in S.I. (Eq. S.24).

$$\varphi_i = \frac{V_{cat}}{A_{cat}} \sqrt{\frac{r_{i,s}''}{D_{eff,i} (C_{i,eq} - C_{i,s})}} \quad (7)$$

$$\eta_i = \frac{r_{i,obs}''}{r_{i,s}''} \quad (8)$$

To assess possible correlations between φ_i and η_i for this system, several simulations were carried out with the rigorous particle model described in previous section, varying the particle size (0.1–20 mm), the temperature (200–270 °C), the pressure (30–40 bar), the catalyst geometry (slab, cylinder, sphere) and the surface concentration. A simplified method to calculate η_i from φ_i is developed in this work, proposing a correlation based on parameters derived via parametric fitting of the simulation results obtained via the rigorous particle model (section 3.1).

2.3. Heat and mass transfer phenomena at the particle–fluid interphase

To account for the film mass/heat transfer at the particle–fluid interphase, in a pseudo-homogeneous reactor model, we solve the steady-state mass (Eq. 9) and heat (Eq. 10 and 11) balances around the catalyst particles. Eq. 9 is solved separately for the CuZA and HZSM-5 particles, which have different surface concentrations ($C_{i,s}$), despite sharing the same bulk conditions ($C_{i,b}$). Eq. 10 and 11 represent the heat balance for the CuZA and HZSM-5 particle, respectively, which have two different surface temperatures ($T_{s,1}$ and $T_{s,2}$). To simplify the calculation of the heat generated in the CuZA particle, we considered that all the CO₂ reacts to CO and that all the methanol is produced via CO hydrogenation.

Table 1

Governing equations for mass and heat conservation in the spherical catalyst particle with radius R_p and the corresponding boundary conditions (B.C.).

Equation	B.C. $r = 0$	B.C. $r = R_p$
Mass balance		
$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(D_{eff,i} \cdot r^2 \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial r} \right) + r_i'' = 0$ (5)	$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial r} = 0$	$C_i = C_{i,b}$ (a)
		$D_{eff,i} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial r} = k_{i,ext} (C_{i,b} - C_{i,s})$ (b)
Heat balance		
$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\lambda_{eff} \cdot r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \sum_{j=1}^N r_j'' (-\Delta H_j) = 0$ (6)	$\frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = 0$	$T = T_b$ (a)
		$\lambda_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = h_{ext} (T_b - T_s)$ (b)

Note that the two catalysts under consideration (i.e., Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ and HZSM-5) catalyze different reactions, and they may present different sizes and porous structure. Thus, the equations are solved for the two particles separately, although the particle size and the radial discretization were assumed the same for simplicity.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the packed bed membrane reactor (bottom left) including the external reactor jacket for the circulation of the boiling water and layout of the 1D-model.

$$\eta_i R_p F_i - k_{i,ext} \cdot (C_{i,b} - C_{i,s}) = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta H_{r2} r_{CO_2,s} \eta_{CO_2} R_p - \Delta H_{r3} r_{MeOH,s} \eta_{MeOH} R_p - h_{ext} \cdot (T_b - T_{s,1}) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$-\Delta H_{r4} r_{DME,s} \eta_{DME} R_p - h_{ext} \cdot (T_b - T_{s,2}) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Finally, the applicability of the Mears criterion was assessed by calculating the relative concentration difference, $(C_{i,b} - C_{i,s})/C_{i,b}$ and the Carberry number (Ca, see S.I. section 4), using the simulation results obtained for different particle sizes (1–20 mm), pressures (30–40 bar), temperatures (200–270 °C), surface compositions and superficial gas velocities (0.001–1 m/s).

2.4. 1D packed bed (membrane) reactor models (heterogeneous and pseudo-homogeneous)

A schematic representation of the packed bed membrane reactor and

of the layout of the model is given in Fig. 1. The complete mass and heat balances as well as the continuity equation (i.e., total mass conservation) in the packed membrane reactor are summarized in Table 2. The same equations apply for the packed bed reactor, when the membrane area per reactor volume (a_{memb}) is zero and there is no distinction between permeation and reaction zones. All equations reported in Table 2 assume plug flow behavior. Deviation from plug flow behavior can be accounted for using the axial dispersion model described in section 2.5.

The mass balance in the reaction zone (Eq. 12) is based on a reaction term (R_i) and a permeation flux ($J_{perm,i}$) of the species through the membrane. The membrane(s) was considered to be placed all along the reactor, thus $L_M = L_R$. The mass balance of the permeation zone (Eq. 13) accounts only for the permeation flux (i.e., no reaction).

The reaction term (R_i) of the Eq. 12, 14 and 15 reported in Table 2 can be described by either Eq. 17, when pore diffusion limitations are modeled with the Thiele modulus approach (i.e., pseudo-homogeneous reactor model) or by Eq. 18, when the concentration profile in the

Table 2

Mass, heat and momentum balance equations and corresponding boundary conditions for the 1D packed bed reactor and packed bed membrane reactor models, in the hypothesis of plug flow. These equations apply for both the heterogeneous and the pseudo-homogeneous reactor models.

Equation	B.C. $z = 0$	B.C. $z = L$
Mass balance – Reaction zone		
$\frac{\partial(v^R C_{i,b}^R)}{\partial z} = R_i - a_{memb} \cdot J_{perm,i}$ (12)	$C_{i,b}^R = C_{i,b}^{R,IN}$	-
Mass balance – Permeation zone		
$\frac{\partial(v^P C_{i,b}^P)}{\partial z} = a_{memb} \cdot J_{perm,i}$ (13)	$C_{i,b}^P = C_{i,b}^{P,IN}$	-
Heat balance (Reaction zone and Permeation zone)		
$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_c} (v^R C_{i,b}^R + v^P C_{i,b}^P) C_{pi} T_b \right) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} R_i (-\Delta H_r) - a_{heat} \cdot U \cdot (T - T_w)$ (14)	$T_b = T_b^{IN}$	-
Continuity equation – Reaction zone		
$-\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\rho_f \frac{\partial P^R}{\partial z} \right) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} (M_i R_i - a_{memb} \cdot J_{perm,i})$ (15)	$\frac{\partial P^R}{\partial z} = \beta_0 v_{in}^R$	$P^R = P_{out}^R$
Continuity equation – Permeation zone		
$-\frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_f v^P) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} (a_{memb} \cdot J_{perm,i})$ (16)	$v^P = v_{in}^P$	-

particle are explicitly solved (i.e., heterogeneous reactor model).

$$R_i = D_{cat}(1 - \epsilon_{bed}) \left(x_{cat1} \Pi_{i,cat1} + x_{cat2} \Pi_{i,cat2} \right) \quad (17)$$

$$R_i = D_{cat}(1 - \epsilon_{bed}) \frac{3}{R_p} \left(x_{cat1} D_{eff,i,cat1} \frac{\partial C_{i,cat1}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_p} + x_{cat2} D_{eff,i,cat2} \frac{\partial C_{i,cat2}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_p} \right) \quad (18)$$

The permeation flux ($J_{perm,i}$) of the species through the membrane is described by Eq. 19.

$$J_{perm,i} = \varphi_i \left(P_{i,sm}^R - P_{i,b}^P \right) \quad (19)$$

Mass transfer limitation in the permeation zone is considered negligible due to the high velocity of the gas in the membrane tubes (i.e., large flow rate due to the sweep gas and small cross section). Thus, the partial pressure in the permeation zone (P_i^P) is considered uniform along the radial direction (i.e., $P_{i,sm}^P = P_{i,b}^P$). On the retentate side, however, when concentration polarization (CP) is relevant, $P_{i,sm}^R$ is different than its bulk value in the reaction zone ($P_{i,b}^R$). Being $k_{CP,i}$ the mass transfer coefficient across the membrane-fluid interphase, the value of $P_{i,sm}^R$ is calculated from the following mass conservation equation:

$$k_{CP,i} \left(C_{i,b}^R - C_{i,sm}^R \right) = \varphi_i \left(P_{i,sm}^R - P_i^P \right) \quad (20)$$

However, specific correlations for $k_{CP,i}$ for this system (i.e., carbon molecular sieve membranes for vapor permeation in a packed bed reactor) do not exist. Thus, a correlation is developed in this work (see section 3.4) using the results of the 2D PBMR model, described in section 2.6. When the CP phenomenon is assumed negligible, the permeation flux in Eq. 21 is calculated considering that $P_{i,sm}^R = P_{i,b}^R$.

Next, a combined heat balance for the reaction and permeation zones (Eq. 14) is adopted since the temperature profile in the two zones is the same (i.e., $T^R = T^P = T$), in line with experimental observations. To approach isothermal conditions, heat removal occurs via the evaporation of water (i.e., latent heat exchange) at constant temperature (T_w), circulating in an external jacket [32].

Finally, Eq. 15 represents the continuity equation of the reaction zone, coupled with Darcy equation (Eq. 21) to determine the pressure drop ($\partial P^R / \partial z$) along the reactor. The friction factor (β) is calculated via the Ergun equation (Eq. 22).

$$v^R = - \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{\partial P^R}{\partial z} \quad (21)$$

$$\beta = 150 \frac{(1 - \epsilon_{bed})^2 \mu_f}{\epsilon_{bed}^3 D_p^2} + 1.75 \frac{\rho_f (1 - \epsilon_{bed}) |v|}{\epsilon_{bed}^2 D_p} \quad (22)$$

The continuity equation for the permeation zone (Eq. 16) is used to determine the velocity profile v^P . The total pressure (P^P) in the permeation zone is assumed constant.

2.5. Axial dispersion model

The axial dispersion model is implemented only in the reaction zone. In the permeation zone, the assumption of plug flow remains (i.e., no solid particles and $L_M / D_M \gg 50$). According to the axial dispersion model, the mass balance and continuity equation in the reaction zone are described by Eq. 23 and Eq. 24, respectively. The heat balance in Eq. 14 (i.e., for plug-flow behavior) remains valid. Axial heat dispersion is seldom significant and often neglected in literature [50].

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(v^R C_{i,b}^R - D_{ax,i} \frac{\partial C_{i,b}^R}{\partial z} \right) = R_i \quad (23)$$

$$- \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\rho_i \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{\partial P^R}{\partial z} \right) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} (M_i R_i - a_{memb} \cdot J_{perm,i}) + \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} M_i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} D_{ax,i} \frac{\partial C_{i,b}^R}{\partial z} \quad (24)$$

The relevance of the axial dispersion is first evaluated in the packed bed reactor (i.e., no membrane, $a_{memb} = 0$) for the sake of simplicity. Under all the explored conditions, conversion and selectivity do not deviate significantly from those under the assumption of plug flow (see S.I.). Thus, axial dispersion is no further considered.

2.6. Mass transfer phenomena at the membrane-fluid interphase (concentration polarization)

2.6.1. 2D isothermal packed bed membrane reactor model

This section describes the 2D PBMR model developed to investigate the relevance of the concentration gradients along the membrane surface (i.e., concentration polarization). This model is pseudo-homogeneous (it uses the adapted Thiele modulus approach to model pore diffusion limitation and mass transfer phenomena in the microporous carbon membrane is assumed to be already included in the permeance). Further, the model assumes:

- 1) In the membrane tube, there is no radial concentration, velocity, pressure and temperature profile.
- 2) The radial component of the velocity is negligible.
- 3) There is no radial pressure profile.
- 4) The velocity in the axial direction is constant along the radius of the reactor.
- 5) There are no angular pressure, concentration, velocity or temperature gradients.

The flow rate in the permeation side is usually the same or even higher ($SW \geq 1$) than the flow rate in the reaction zone, combined with a much smaller cross section ($L_M / D_M \gg 50$). Such conditions do not favor radial concentration, velocity, pressure and temperature profiles. In reality, the velocity in the radial direction in the reaction zone is not zero due to the permeation flux. Therefore, neglecting the radial component of the velocity could lead to poor results [51]. However, the radial dispersion coefficient used in this model also partially accounts for a flux in the radial direction. In literature, it is very common to neglect the radial pressure profile [43,51]. Thus we also neglected it in this work. Furthermore, when the particle diameter is sufficiently small compared to the reactor diameter (i.e., $D_{ri} / D_p \gg 15$), the bed porosity can be considered uniform in the radial direction, resulting in flat profiles of the axial velocity, along the reactor radius [52]. To simplify the implementation of the 2D model, we considered a PBMR with one membrane placed at the center of the reaction zone. Thus, the reactor is symmetrical around the axis, which also avoids angular gradients, as well as to a zero contribution of the angular component of the velocity. Finally, since there are already well-established correlations to describe the heat

Table 3

Governing equations and boundary conditions for the mass balances in the reaction and permeation zone of the 2D pseudo-homogeneous isothermal PBMR model.

Equation	Boundary conditions
Mass balance – Reaction zone	
$\frac{\partial (v^R C_i^R)}{\partial z} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r D_{rad,i} \frac{\partial C_i^R}{\partial r} \right) = R_i$ (25)	@ $z = 0$
	$C_i^R = C_i^{R,IN}$
	@ $r = R_{ri}$ @ $r = R_{mo}$
	$\frac{\partial C_i^R}{\partial r} = 0$ $D_{rad,i} \frac{\partial C_i^R}{\partial r} = \varphi_i (P_i^R - P_i^P)$
Mass balance – Permeation zone	
Eq. 13	@ $z = 0$
	$C_i^P = C_i^{P,IN}$

transfer to the reactor wall, and the radial heat transfer from/to the membrane is considered negligible, the 2D PBMR model is considered isothermal (i.e., nor radial or axial temperature profiles). This is done to simplify the model implementation and the analysis of the results as well as to isolate and study the CP phenomena, avoiding any nuisance that may be caused by temperature gradients.

The mass balance equations for the reaction and permeation zone, together with their boundary conditions are reported in Table 3. The mass balance equation for the permeation zone is the same as Eq. 13. The mass balance equation in the reaction zone (Eq. 25) does not directly account for the permeation flux, since the permeation of species occurs at the boundary between the reaction and permeation zone. Thus, the permeation flux is incorporated in the boundary condition (i.e., @ $r = R_{mo}$). The second boundary condition for Eq. 28 along the radial direction imposes that the flux at $r = R_{ri}$ is zero, since there is no mass flux through the reactor walls.

2.6.2. Fitted Sherwood-type correlation for the CP mass transfer coefficient

Alternatively to the 2D PBMR model, the concentration polarization phenomenon could be accounted for via the definition of a mass transfer coefficient (k_{CP}) determined via correlations, as described in section 2.4. Boon et al. [43] proposed a correlation to estimate the mass transfer coefficient for the H_2 separation via palladium membranes in an empty column (i.e., gas separation process with no reaction). However, with this correlation, the concentration polarization effect on the reaction performance is significantly underestimated (see S.I.). To the best of our knowledge, in literature there is no correlation describing the CP phenomenon for carbon molecular sieve membranes, especially when they are implemented in a packed bed reactor (i.e., PBMR). Thus, we developed a Sherwood-type correlation (Eq. 26–27) for the calculation of the k_{CP} , as follows:

$$Sh = a Re^b Sc^c E^d \quad (26)$$

$$Sh = \frac{k_{CP,i} d_h}{D_m} \quad (27)$$

In Eq. 26 a, b, c and d are the coefficients of the correlation that have to be determined via parametric fitting, E is a dimensionless number which accounts for entrance effects and d_h is a characteristic length which we defined as the space between the reactor wall and the membrane selective layer (i.e., $d_h = R_{ri} - R_{mo}$).

The mass transfer coefficient $k_{CP,i}$ was determined from the 2D PBMR simulation results, via Eq. 28.

$$k_{CP,i} = \frac{J_{perm,i}}{\langle C_{i,r} \rangle - C_{i,sm}} \quad (28)$$

Using the definition of the $k_{CP,i}$ from Eq. 33, in combination with Eq. 29, a set of 6800 data of Sherwood numbers was obtained from the results of the 2D PBMR simulations, carried out under a wide range of conditions. These include variations of the GHSV (10 – 2000 h^{-1}), the temperature (200 – $270 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), the pressure (30 – 40 bar), the SW (0.5 – 2), the inlet composition to both zones ($H_2:CO_2$ of 1 – 4), the reactor length

Table 4

Cases description for the Sherwood number correlation for the mass transfer coefficient $k_{CP,i}$.

Case #	Sh correlation	Sc definition
1	$Sh = a Re^b Sc^c \left(\frac{d_h}{z}\right)^d$	$Sc = \frac{\mu_i}{\rho_i D_{m,i}}$
2	$Sh = a Re^b Sc^c (Pe_{ent})^d$	$Sc = \frac{\mu_i}{\rho_i D_{m,i}}$
3	$Sh = a Re^b Sc^c (Pe_{ent})^d$	$Sc = \frac{\mu_i}{\rho_i D_{rad}}$
4	$Sh = a Re^b Sc^c (Pe_{ent})^d$	$Sc = \frac{\mu_i}{\rho_i D_{rad}}$
	$Sh = a Re^b Sc^c$	for $Pe_{ent} > 1$
		for $Pe_{ent} \leq 1$

(0.1 – 10 m), the reactor diameter (0.02 – 1 m), the particle diameter (0.1 – 20 mm), the membrane diameter (5 – 20 mm) and the zeolite weight fraction (0.25 – 0.75). The parameters of the Sh correlation (Eq. 26) were determined via parametric fitting of the Sh numbers obtained from the rigorous 2D model.

The parameters were fitted in four different cases (Table 4), which consider two alternatives for the term E (i.e., d_h/z or Pe_{ent} of Eq. 29) and two definitions of the Schmidt number (Sc). Finally, in case 4, the dependency on the entrance effect is removed when the concentration profiles are fully developed (i.e., for $Pe_{ent} \leq 1$).

$$Pe_{ent} = \frac{v d_h^2}{z D_{rad}} \quad (29)$$

2.7. Reactor performance indicators

The reactor performance indicators in terms of CO_2 conversion, product yield and selectivity are summarized in Eq. 30–32, where the loss or cofeeding of reactants (i.e., through back-permeation of sweep gas in the reaction zone) is considered as reported in our previous study [31]. The extent of water removal in the PBMR is quantified according to Eq. 36.

$$X_{CO_2} = \frac{F_{CO_2,0}^R - F_{CO_2}^R + F_{CO_2,tmb}}{F_{CO_2,0}^R + F_{CO_2,tmb}^*} \quad (30)$$

$$Y_i = \frac{N_{c,i} (F_i^R + F_i^P)}{F_{CO_2,0}^R + F_{CO_2,tmb}^*} \quad (31)$$

$$S_i = \frac{Y_i}{X_{CO_2}} \quad (32)$$

$$F_{CO_2,tmb} = F_{CO_2,0}^P - F_{CO_2}^P \quad CO_2 \text{ transmembrane flow} \quad (33)$$

$$F_{CO_2,tmb}^* = 0 \quad \text{if } F_{CO_2,tmb} \leq 0 \quad \text{Reactant loss} \quad (34)$$

$$F_{CO_2,tmb}^* = F_{CO_2,tmb} \quad \text{if } F_{CO_2,tmb} > 0 \quad \text{Reactant cofeeding} \quad (35)$$

$$WR = \frac{F_{H_2O}^P}{F_{H_2O}^P + F_{H_2O}^R} \quad (36)$$

2.8. Model implementation and numerical method

The Newton Raphson method with a central differencing scheme was implemented in MATLAB R2019a to solve numerically the system of equations. A grid size optimization was carried out for the different domains (i.e., particle, reactor). In some cases, a non-uniform grid refinement was required in the regions with steeper gradients (i.e., near the reactor wall or at the catalyst surface). All the models were verified comparing the numerical solutions with the analytical counter-parts for simplified system (i.e., first order irreversible and elemental reaction $A \rightarrow B$), and by checking total mass conservation.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of intra-particle heat and mass transfer phenomena

3.1.1. Particle model approach

To assess the relevance of the intra-particle diffusion phenomena, the concentration profiles in the catalyst particles were first determined in a limiting case. Thus, simulations were run with a particle diameter of 10 mm and at a reaction temperature of $270 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to guarantee a longer diffusion path and fast reaction rates, respectively. Fig. 2 shows that in this scenario, in both catalyst particles, the concentration gradients of products and reactant are quite significant, particularly for the DME

Fig. 2. Concentration of reactants (left axis) and products (right axis) in the CuZA (a) and HZSM-5 catalyst (b) particles ($T_{\text{surf}} = 270$ °C, $P=40$ bar, $d_p=10$ mm).

catalyst (Fig. 2b). Indeed, the HZSM-5 particles have very small pores (i.e., average pore size of ca. 3 nm), which explain the lower diffusion rates. Furthermore, the methanol dehydration reaction is faster than methanol synthesis, which makes the diffusion step more limiting, thus leading to steeper concentration gradients. As a result, internal mass transfer phenomena can become limiting in realistic conditions (i.e., particle size relevant to industrial applications and at higher temperatures, which can easily develop in non-isothermal operation). Thus, these phenomena must be included in the reactor model to obtain more reliable predictions of the reaction performance.

On the contrary, internal temperature gradients were found negligible even when simulated in a limiting condition (i.e., fast heat production due to the fast reaction rate and slow heat diffusion rate). The maximum temperature difference between the center and the surface of the particle was found to be ca. 0.1 °C for both catalysts (see S.I.), which corresponds to a relative difference of less than 0.01%. This result is in agreement with literature, since the absence of internal heat transfer limitations is often observed in similar systems [53]. Being the temperature gradients not significant even in a critical situation, the catalyst particles can be considered isothermal.

3.1.2. Development of the Thiele modulus-efficiency approach

The φ_i and η_i evaluated using Eq. 7 and 8 from the simulation results

of the rigorous particle model correlates in a similar way as for 1st order kinetic reactions, as depicted in Fig. 3a and b for the methanol and DME catalyst, respectively. To check if the observed correlation is general, the same analysis was carried out using different kinetic models describing the methanol synthesis, such as the kinetics from Bussche & Froment [54], Graaf et al. [55], Henkel [56], Park [56] and the kinetic derived by us in a previous study [57]. We found that the correlation still holds even when considering different kinetics.

However, this correlation does not hold for CO, which is not reported here (see S.I.). CO is an intermediate product of the methanol synthesis, meaning that its profile in the methanol catalyst particle is not monotonically increasing/decreasing vs the radius of the particle. On the contrary, it displays a maximum or minimum value, according to the temperature conditions. This means that CO could diffuse in multiple directions in the catalyst particle, which is something that it is not taken into account in the definition of the Thiele modulus. Nevertheless, the methanol synthesis requires only two independent components, which means that the efficiency of CO can be eventually derived via mass balance, as follows:

$$2\eta_{\text{CO}}r'_{\text{CO},\text{surf}} = \eta_{\text{H}_2}r'_{\text{H}_2,\text{surf}} - 3\eta_{\text{CO}_2}r'_{\text{CO}_2,\text{surf}} \quad (42)$$

To mathematically describe the η_i - φ_i correlation, we define the following function:

Fig. 3. Catalyst efficiency (η_i) as a function of the Thiele modulus (φ_i) for the different species in both methanol catalyst (a) and DME catalyst (b) for systems with varying particle geometry (slab, cylinder, sphere), temperature (200–270 °C), pressure (30–40 bar), particle size (0.1–20 mm) and surface compositions. Dashed lines indicate the point of significant deviation of η_i from 1.

Table 5
Coefficients a and b for Eq. 43 and dependency of a on the effective diffusivity.

Component	Catalyst	a	b	$10^6 \cdot D_{\text{eff},i}$	$10^6 \cdot \frac{a}{D_{\text{eff},i}}$	$a \cdot \frac{D_{\text{eff},\text{lim}}}{D_{\text{eff},i}}$
Spherical geometry						
CO ₂	CuZA	1.09	0.47	1.07	1.02	0.99
H ₂	CuZA	3.07	0.50	2.76	1.11	1.08
MeOH	CuZA	0.89	0.54	0.97	0.92	0.89
H ₂ O	CuZA	1.56	0.46	1.36	1.15	1.11
DME	HZSM-5	1.03	0.48	0.42	2.44	1.03
MeOH	HZSM-5	1.28	0.48	0.53	2.44	1.03
H ₂ O	HZSM-5	1.80	0.48	0.74	2.44	1.03
Cylindrical geometry						
CO ₂	CuZA	0.86	0.50	1.07	0.80	0.91
H ₂	CuZA	2.63	0.52	2.76	0.95	1.08
MeOH	CuZA	0.86	0.55	1.13	0.76	0.86
H ₂ O	CuZA	1.22	0.50	1.36	0.90	1.01
DME	HZSM-5	1.00	0.51	0.42	2.37	1.00
MeOH	HZSM-5	1.08	0.51	0.45	2.37	1.00
H ₂ O	HZSM-5	1.51	0.51	1.64	2.37	1.00
Slab geometry						
CO ₂	CuZA	1.00	0.53	1.07	0.94	0.91
H ₂	CuZA	2.74	0.54	2.76	0.99	0.97
MeOH	CuZA	0.96	0.55	0.97	0.99	0.96
H ₂ O	CuZA	1.40	0.53	1.36	1.03	1.00
DME	HZSM-5	0.96	0.53	0.42	2.27	0.96
MeOH	HZSM-5	1.03	0.53	0.45	2.27	0.96
H ₂ O	HZSM-5	1.45	0.53	0.64	2.28	0.96

$$\eta_i = \frac{1}{(1 + a \varphi_i^2)^b} \quad (39)$$

According to Eq. 39, η_i approaches 1 for small value of φ_i (i.e., kinetic limiting regime) and approaches 0 for very large values of φ_i (i.e., diffusion limiting regime), which is the expected physical behavior.

The values of a and b derived via parametric fitting of the curves displayed in Fig. 3 with Eq. 39 are reported in Table 5.

The fitted value of b is close to 0.5 independently of the component, catalyst and particle geometry. This value indicates that for larger value of φ_i , such that $a \varphi_i^2 \gg 1$, η_i scales linearly with $1/\varphi_i$. This behavior is also observed with the effectiveness factor analytically derived for 1st order reaction.

The parameter a changes significantly per component and catalyst type, but it does not depend on the particle geometry. In particular, the value of the parameter a was found to be equal to the ratio $D_{\text{eff},i}/D_{\text{eff},\text{lim}}$, where $D_{\text{eff},\text{lim}}$ is the diffusivity of the slowest diffusing component in each catalyst particle. Thus, the formula for the component-specific ef-

iciency we propose is the following:

$$\eta_i = \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{D_{\text{eff},i}}{D_{\text{eff},\text{lim}}} \varphi_i^2\right)^{0.5}} \quad (43)$$

The dependency of η_i on the $D_{\text{eff},\text{lim}}$ is also physically reasonable, since the reactive system is more affected by the slowest diffusing species. The parity plot representing the quality of the fit of Eq. 43 with respect to the efficiency derived via the rigorous particle model is reported in S.I.

3.2. Effect of fluid-particle heat and mass transfer phenomena

As for the intra-particle heat and mass transfer phenomena, also the relevance of the film mass and heat transfer was first evaluated in a limiting scenario. These phenomena could be limiting in a scenario with fast kinetic (i.e., high reaction temperature) combined with large catalyst particle and low superficial velocity (v_{sf}). As a result, simulations were first run at 270 °C, with a particle diameter of 10 mm and varying the superficial velocity in the range 0.001–10 m/s. The results are

Fig. 4. Normalized surface concentration ($C_{i,\text{surf}}/C_{i,\text{bulk}}$) for the different components (a) and normalized surface temperature ($T_{\text{surf}}/T_{\text{bulk}}$) (b) of the CuZA (circles) and HZSM-5 (stars) catalysts as a function of the superficial gas velocity determined at a bulk temperature of 270 °C, a pressure of 40 bar and a particle diameter of 10 mm. The dashed lines represent a 1% deviation from 1.

Fig. 5. Relative concentration difference between the catalyst surface and the bulk fluid as a function of the Carberry number obtained for different particle sizes (1–20 mm), pressures (30–40 bar), temperatures (200–270 °C), surface compositions and superficial gas velocities (0.001–1 m/s). The vertical dashed line corresponds to $Ca = 0.15$, the horizontal dashed line corresponds to $(C_{i,\text{bulk}} - C_{i,\text{surf}})/C_{i,\text{bulk}} = 0.05$ (i.e., Mears criterion).

reported in terms of normalized surface concentration ($C_{i,\text{surf}}/C_{i,\text{bulk}}$) and temperature ($T_{\text{surf}}/T_{\text{bulk}}$), as a function of v_{sf} (Fig. 4a and b, respectively). The two reference lines displayed in Fig. 4 represent a 1% deviation from

1, which corresponds to the scenario in which the external mass and heat transfer phenomena are fast enough, thus not limiting. Fig. 4a shows that at low superficial velocity (i.e., below 0.2 m/s), the external mass

Fig. 6. CO_2 conversion (a) and product selectivity (b) as a function of the particle diameter, at a reaction temperature of 270 °C and CO_2 conversion (c) and product selectivity (d) as a function of the reaction temperature, with a particle diameter of 10 mm. Other conditions are: $P_{\text{in}}^R = 40$ bar, $(\text{C}_{\text{H}_2}/\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2})_{\text{in,bulk}} = 3$, $\text{GHSV} = 500 \text{ h}^{-1}$, $w_{\text{cat}1} = 0.5$.

transfer has a significant effect, with surface concentration deviating up to 6% from the concentration in the bulk phase.

On the contrary, the temperature gradients are, once again, not significant, with $T_{\text{surf}}/T_{\text{bulk}}$ approaching 1 even for very low velocities (Fig. 4b). Usually, in gas phase reactions with solid porous catalysts, the external heat transfer is slower than the external mass transfer, due to the very low thermal conductivity of the gases [34]. However, H_2 has a relatively high thermal conductivity (i.e., in the order of 0.2 W/m/K) with respect to other gases (i.e., in the order of 0.03 W/m/K). This explains the absence of any film ΔT even in a limiting situation. As a matter of fact, when the H_2 thermal conductivity is artificially set as the conductivity of CO_2 , the simulation results show that the temperature gradients in the particle–fluid interphase can be significant. (see S.I.).

Furthermore, Fig. 5 shows that for $Ca < 0.15$, $(C_{i,\text{bulk}} - C_{i,\text{surf}}) / C_{i,\text{bulk}} < 0.05$ holds for both catalyst particles, which means that this criterion is applicable also to our system, despite its complexity. As a result, the Mears criterion could be implemented in the reactor model, to evaluate a priori whether the film concentration gradient is significant and must be taken into account. Nevertheless, the implementation of Eq. 9, together with the Thiele-modulus approach does not add significant complexity to the reactor model, thus this phenomenon could be considered regardless of its relevance.

3.3. Effect of the relevant mass/heat transfer phenomena at reactor scale

3.3.1. Small scale PBR

To assess the effect of the internal diffusion limitations on the packed bed reactor performance, simulations were run under isothermal conditions and in two scenarios: 1) at 270 °C, varying the particle diameter in the range 0.25–20 mm; 2) using a particle diameter of 10 mm, varying the temperature in the range 200–270 °C. The analysis was done at a relatively high space velocity (i.e., GHSV of 500 h^{-1}), to prevent the system to achieve thermodynamic equilibrium. This corresponds to a situation where both the kinetics and mass transfer do not affect the performance anymore. Fig. 6a and b show that at large catalyst particle diameter (≥ 1 mm) and at high temperature (≥ 220 °C), the CO_2 conversion determined via the heterogeneous reactor model (i.e., solving the particle model) deviates significantly from the conversion determined under the hypothesis of kinetically limited regime (i.e., without internal mass transfer, MT_{INT}) up to a maximum of 5%. Similarly, the selectivity towards DME (Fig. 6c and d) decreases when the system is affected by the pore diffusion rate. At the same time, methanol selectivity increases, which indicates that the HZSM-5 catalyst is more affected by internal diffusion, as previously observed.

Furthermore, Fig. 6 shows that the Thiele modulus approach (circles) predicts with high accuracy the trend in CO_2 conversion and product selectivity computed via the heterogeneous reactor model (stars) in the range of $D_p = 0$ –3 mm and $T = 200$ –250 °C.

In severely diffusion limited regime (i.e., particle diameter larger than 5 mm and temperature above 250 °C), the Thiele modulus approach tends to overestimate the effect of internal mass transfer, resulting in a lower conversion compared to that obtained when solving the heterogeneous model. The product selectivity, instead, is predicted with high accuracy over the entire range of explored conditions. Nevertheless, it must be noted that the largest deviations observed in the CO_2 conversion correspond to the least realistic conditions. Indeed, in industry, particle size of ca. 3 mm are commonly used, while temperatures above 250 °C corresponds to very low DME selectivity (i.e., rWGS favored).

The relative error between the solution of the heterogeneous (i.e., particle-reactor) and of the pseudo-homogeneous (i.e., Thiele modulus approach) model was determined in all the conditions. Such error was found to exceed 5% for the CO_2 conversion, when the maximum Thiele modulus in the system is larger than 2. This situation corresponds to an effectiveness factor of ca. 90%.

The effect of the external mass transfer was assessed in a similar way, carrying out isothermal reactor simulations at the same conditions of section 3.2 and with a GHSV of 500 h^{-1} . We observed that the CO_2 conversion and product selectivity are barely affected by the velocities in the range 0.001–10 m/s. Indeed, at the lowest velocity, we calculated a maximum deviation in the DME selectivity and methanol yield of 3.5% (see S.I.). As a consequence, considering that an inlet superficial velocity of 0.001 m/s, a temperature of 270 °C and a particle diameter of 10 mm are not common for this system, we conclude that the film concentration gradients are not relevant at reactor scale. Thus, also the external mass transfer phenomena can be neglected.

The relevance of the axial dispersion was also assessed running isothermal simulations in a limiting condition (i.e., high axial dispersion coefficient, D_{ax}). D_{ax} depends on the molecular diffusivity, particle diameter and fluid velocity, similarly to the external mass transfer coefficient (see S.I.). In particular, D_{ax} increases for larger particle diameters and becomes more relevant as the superficial gas velocity increases. Thus, simulations were run with a particle diameter of 10 mm and varying the superficial gas velocity. Furthermore, a temperature of 270 °C was selected to ensure fast reaction rates.

However, in all the explored conditions, conversion and selectivity did not show significant deviations from the results obtained under the assumption of plug flow (see S.I.). Therefore, this phenomenon can be neglected and plug flow will be considered a valid assumption for the rest of this study.

3.3.2. Large scale PBR and PBMR

In this section, we discuss the effect of intra-particle diffusion phenomena on the performance of the PBR and PBMR at relevant operating conditions (i.e., temperature, pressure) and at a space velocity which is compatible with industrial scale (i.e., which guarantees approach to thermodynamic equilibrium). Reaction conditions were selected based on preliminary simulations and reactor scale-up/optimization reported in our previous study [32], carried out with simplified models, which do not consider any effect of internal/external mass and heat transfer phenomena.

The reaction conditions used to simulate the PBR and PBMR are reported in Table 6. A detailed discussion on the selection of these conditions, as well as on the optimization and sizing procedure adopted for the PBR and PBMR is already reported in our previous work [32]. A GHSV of 32.11 h^{-1} was found sufficient to approach the thermodynamic equilibrium in the PBR for a catalytic bed composed of 50 wt% of HZSM-5. The mass fraction of zeolite has often been found to not significantly

Table 6
Reaction conditions and reactor geometry used for the PBR and PBMR simulations.

Reactor property/condition	Unit	Value PBR	Value PBMR
Inlet temperature (T^{IN})	°C	200	200
Inlet pressure reaction zone ($P^{\text{R,IN}}$)	bar	40	40
GHSV	h^{-1}	32.11	32.11
Feed $H_2:CO_2$ ratio	mol/mol	3	3
Cooling water temperature (T_w)	°C	188	176
Reactor length (L_R)	m	18.23	17.72
Reactor inner diameter (D_{ri})	m	3.65	3.54
Reactor outer diameter (D_{ro})	m	3.81	3.70
Membrane area per reactor volume (a_{memb})	$m^2_{\text{memb}}/m^3_{\text{reac}}$	–	2.631
Pressure gradient across the membrane (ΔP)	bar	–	5
Sweep gas flow ratio (SW)	–	–	1
Sweep gas $H_2:CO_2$ ratio	mol/mol	–	3
Bed porosity (ϵ_{bed})	$m^3_{\text{void}}/m^3_{\text{reac}}$	0.4	0.4
Catalyst dilution factor (D_{cat})	$m^3_{\text{SiC}}/m^3_{\text{cat}}$	0.66	0.66
Zeolite weight fraction (w_{cat2})	$kg_{\text{cat2}}/kg_{\text{cat}}$	0.5	0.5
Catalyst particle diameter (D_p)	mm	3	3

Table 7

PBR and PBMR performance determined with the conditions of Table 7 with a 1D pseudo-homogeneous kinetically limited (no MT_{INT}) model and with a 1D pseudo-homogeneous model accounting for pore diffusion phenomena with the Thiele modulus approach (with MT_{INT}).

Reactor performance	PBR – no MT_{INT}	PBR with MT_{INT}	PBMR – no MT_{INT}	PBMR with MT_{INT}
CO ₂ conversion	37.96%	37.95%	52.28%	52.27%
DME selectivity	83.71%	83.8%	97%	97%
MeOH selectivity	13.42%	13.36%	0%	0%
CO selectivity	2.87%	2.84%	3%	3%

influence the overall reaction performance, being the system limited by the methanol synthesis. Thus, values between 33 and 50% are often proposed in literature (i.e., CuZA/HZSM-5 ratio between 1 and 2) [58–60].

Table 7 reports the corresponding reactor performance for both the PBR and PBMR evaluated both with a simplified model (i.e., model which does not account for internal mass transfer phenomena, INMT) and with the model described in section 2.4 (i.e., pseudo-homogeneous model with Thiele modulus approach). From these results, we observe that the intra-particle diffusion phenomena have no significant effect on the performance of both reactors in these conditions.

These results were obtained assuming a particle size which is typically employed in industry for these system (i.e., 3 mm). Interestingly, even when increasing the D_p to 10 mm, the reduction in the CO₂ conversion and DME yield is less than 0.88% and 0.65%, respectively (see Appendix E). This result is, seemingly, not in line with the findings from Section 3.1, where it was showed that at sufficiently large D_p (i.e., 4–10 mm), the efficiency of the catalyst particles is significantly reduced. This occurs already at 200 °C for the HZSM-5 particle, where the efficiency can drop to 90% for D_p of 10 mm.

To investigate why the intra-particle mass transfer does not affect the performance of both reactors, we calculated the catalyst efficiency for both the CuZA and HZSM-5 particles over the length of the PBMR (Fig. 7a). From this analysis, we observe that the efficiency of both catalysts initially decreases, due to an increase in the reaction temperature in the first section of the reactor (see chapter 2 for typical temperature profile). Thereafter, the efficiency increases again, displaying an average value of 98% and 21% for the CuZA and HZSM-5, respectively. As a result, the pore diffusion has a little effect on the methanol synthesis, but it should significantly affect the production of DME, which is not the case, as we saw in Table 7.

This suggests that the limitation for the methanol dehydration

Fig. 7. Catalyst efficiency (a) and methanol real (i.e., in the reactor) and equilibrium concentration (b) for both the CuZA (left axis) and HZSM-5 (right axis) as a function of the reactor length. Simulations were carried out on a PBMR, under the conditions reported in Table 7, using a catalyst particle diameter of 3 mm and T_w of 176 °C.

Fig. 8. Optimal zeolite weight fraction (%) as a function of the catalyst particle diameters for both the PBR and PBMR, determined with a model which does not consider the intra-particle mass transfer (No MT_{INT}) and for a model which accounts for internal mass transfer limitation (MT_{INT}). Simulations were run under isothermal conditions (220C) and at GHSV = 1000 h⁻¹. Other conditions are reported in Table 6.

reaction lies somewhere else. Indeed, in Fig. 7b we observe that the actual DME concentration in the PBMR corresponds to the thermodynamic equilibrium, which indicates that the reaction is limited by thermodynamics. As a consequence, a lower or higher reaction rate would not result in any change in the methanol conversion to DME, since the reaction is already sufficiently fast to achieve its thermodynamic equilibrium. Thus, the reduced rate due to the low catalyst efficiency does not affect the reaction performance. Fig. 7b also shows that the methanol concentration along the PBMR is always lower than its thermodynamic value. This, together with the high CuZA efficiency (i.e., 98%) suggests that the methanol synthesis is a kinetically limited system, under these conditions.

Being the methanol dehydration limited by thermodynamics, a fraction of the zeolite bed could be removed from the reactor, without any effect on the overall reaction performance. Indeed, if we remove ca. 90 wt% of the HZSM-5 from the catalyst bed, the DME concentration along the PBMR shifts downwards with respect to the equilibrium curve (see S.I.), with a corresponding increase in the contribution of the pore-

diffusion phenomena to the reaction rate.

Based on these findings, the $w_{\text{cat}2}$ was optimized for both the PBR and PBMR and for different catalyst particle size, as reported in Fig. 8. When water is removed from the reaction environment (PBMR), the optimal zeolite fraction was found to be slightly higher (ca. 0.5%), because the membrane alters the equilibrium of the system, reducing the water concentration. As a consequence, the methanol concentration is higher, resulting in the formation of more DME (i.e., dynamic equilibrium). Thus, a larger fraction of zeolite is required to achieve the dynamic equilibrium conditions in the membrane reactor.

Furthermore, when the effects of intra-particle diffusion phenomena are accounted for, for $D_p > 0.5$ mm, the optimal zeolite fraction increases with the particle size. Indeed, with larger catalyst particles, the effect of mass transfer becomes more significant, resulting in a lower methanol dehydration reaction rate. As a consequence, a larger fraction of HZSM-5 is required to achieve the equilibrium both in the PBR and PBMR. This result is of high relevance, since the effect of the zeolite mass fraction can be significantly underestimated and considered negligible, as often reported in literature [58,61], when the intra-particle diffusion limitations are not considered, especially for the HZSM-5.

The optimal zeolite weight fraction depends on the catalyst particle size and on the extent of water removal, as well as on the operating temperature and pressure. Thus, the optimization should be carried out for each specific set of conditions.

3.4. Effect of the concentration polarization phenomena

3.4.1. Evaluation of the CP phenomena via the 2D PBMR model

Similarly to the previous sections, we first assessed whether the concentration polarization phenomenon (i.e., fluid-membrane surface mass transfer) is relevant in a limiting situation. As a result, 2D PBMR simulations were carried out at high temperature (270 °C), to ensure a higher permeation flux, combined with small catalyst particle diameter ($D_p = 0.25$ mm) and low gas velocity (i.e., $v^R = 0.001$ m/s), to reduce the mass transfer rate in the radial direction. These conditions result in significant radial concentration gradients as depicted in Fig. 9. Water (Fig. 9b) shows a particularly steep gradient close to the membrane surface, due to its high permeation flux (i.e., highest permeance, combined with a significant driving force). Similarly, all the species which are not circulated in the sweep gas show a steeper gradient, due to their higher permeation flux.

The water concentration profile hinders the effectiveness of the membrane, by reducing the effective driving force which determines the

permeation flux. As a result, the PBMR performance could significantly change when this phenomenon is accounted for, as depicted in Fig. 10. At higher temperatures, the effect of the concentration polarization on the CO₂ conversion becomes quite significant, despite being negligible on the product selectivity. Nevertheless, even if the efficiency of the membrane is reduced, the PBMR still outperforms the PBR.

3.4.2. Development of the CP mass transfer coefficient approach

The parameters of the Sh correlation determined via parametric fitting of the of the Sh numbers obtained from the rigorous 2D model, using the correlations proposed in Table 4, show a quality of the fit progressively improving from case 1 to 4 (i.e., $F_{\text{statistic}}$ decreases from 0.1456 to 0.1370), as reported in S.I..

The factor d_h/z used to account for entrance effects in case 1, is not completely representative of the phenomena occurring at the reactor entrance. In particular, the entrance effect should account for two phenomena: 1) how fast the concentration profile develops (i.e., rate of mass transfer in the radial direction), 2) the residence time of the fluid in the reactor. The Peclet number (Pe_{ent}) defined as in Eq. 34, combines these two aspects, comparing the characteristic time for dispersion in the radial direction (d_h^2/D_{rad}), with the characteristic time for convection in the axial direction (z/v). Thus, this explain the improvement in the quality of the fit when going from case 1 to case 2.

The correlation is further improved with case 3, where the molecular diffusivity ($D_{m,i}$) in the Schmidt number (Sc) is replaced with the radial dispersion coefficient (D_{rad}). Indeed, D_{rad} also accounts for the particle size and the tortuosity of the catalytic bed, which are parameters that are expected to affect the mass transfer in the radial direction.

Finally, in case 4, we propose two expression for the Sh, defined in two different regimes: 1) for $Pe_{\text{ent}} > 1$, the concentration profiles are not developed, thus the correlation needs to account for the entrance effect with the term $(Pe_{\text{ent}})^d$; 2) for $Pe_{\text{ent}} \leq 1$, the profiles are already developed, thus the dependency on the Pe_{ent} is removed.

The parameters that were obtained with case 4 are summarized in Table 8 and the quality of the fit is reported in terms of parity plot and $F_{\text{statistic}}$ in S.I.. The values of all the parameters are in line with the range commonly proposed in literature for these types of correlations [34,53]. Furthermore, the exponent of the Schmidt number (c) is close to 0.33, which is a recurrent value in the state of the art mass transfer correlations. Indeed, the term $Sc^{0.33}$ derives from the analytical solution of similar problems. Therefore, we propose a refitting of the parameters, setting the value of c to 0.33, being this an assumption with theoretical basis. The values of a, b and d obtained do not deviate much from the

Fig. 9. Radial concentration profiles of the reactants (a) and products (b) determined via the 2D PBMR model at $z = L/2$. Operating conditions: $T^R = 270$ °C, $p^{R,IN} = 40$ bar, $(C_{H_2}/C_{CO_2})_{in} = 3$, GHSV = 50 h⁻¹, $w_{\text{cat}1} = 0.5$ wt.%, $\Delta P = 5$ bar, SW = 1, $D_p = 0.25$ mm, $L_R = 0.5$ m, $D_{ri} = 0.1$ m, $D_{mo} = 0.01$ m.

Fig. 10. CO₂ conversion (a) and product selectivity (b) for a PBR (dashed lines) and a PBMR evaluated via a 1D model (solid line) and a 2D model (stars). Operating conditions: $T^R = 270$ °C, $P^{R,IN} = 40$ bar, $(C_{H_2}/C_{CO_2})_{in} = 3$, $GHSV = 50$ h⁻¹, $w_{cat1} = 0.5$ wt.%, $\Delta P = 5$ bar, $SW = 1$, $D_p = 0.25$ mm, $L_R = 0.5$ m, $D_{ri} = 0.1$ m, $D_{mo} = 0.01$ m.

Table 8

Fitted parameters for Eq. 29– Case 4.

Parameter	Value	Refitted value
a	0.4628	0.4338
b	0.3509	0.3583
c	0.3179	0.3330
d	0.2640	0.2634

previous set of parameters and the quality of the fit is not affected. The final correlation we propose for the calculation of the $k_{CP,i}$ is summarized in Eq. 44–45.

$$Sh = 0.43 \left(\frac{\rho_1 v_{SF} d_h}{\mu_1 \varepsilon_{bed}} \right)^{0.36} \left(\frac{\mu_1}{\rho_1 D_{rad}} \right)^{0.33} \left(\frac{v d_h^2}{z D_{rad}} \right)^{0.26} \quad \text{for } Pe_{ent} > 1 \quad (44)$$

$$Sh = 0.43 \left(\frac{\rho_1 v_{SF} d_h}{\mu_1 \varepsilon_{bed}} \right)^{0.36} \left(\frac{\mu_1}{\rho_1 D_{rad}} \right)^{0.33} \quad \text{for } Pe_{ent} \leq 1 \quad (45)$$

The results reported in Fig. 10 were reproduced using the 1D PBMR model developed in section 2.4 using Eq. 21, combined with Eq. 22, for the definition of the permeation flux ($J_{perm,i}$).

Fig. 11. CO₂ conversion (a) and product selectivity (b) for a PBMR evaluated via a 1D model which does not account for CP phenomenon (solid line), a 2D model (stars) and a 1D model which accounts for the CP phenomenon using the correlation developed in this section (circles). Operating conditions: $T^R = 270$ °C, $P^{R,IN} = 40$ bar, $(C_{H_2}/C_{CO_2})_{in} = 3$, $GHSV = 50$ h⁻¹, $w_{cat1} = 0.5$ wt.%, $\Delta P = 5$ bar, $SW = 1$, $D_p = 0.25$ mm, $L_R = 0.5$ m, $D_{ri} = 0.1$ m, $D_{mo} = 0.01$ m.

Fig. 12. Difference of CO₂ conversion and product selectivity between a model which does not account for the CP phenomenon and a model that accounts for it via the Sh correlation. Operating conditions of the PBMR: $T^R = 270^\circ C$, $P^{R,IN} = 40$ bar, $(C_{H_2}/C_{CO_2})_{in} = 3$, $GHSV = 50$ h⁻¹, $w_{cat1} = 0.5$ wt.%, $\Delta P = 5$ bar, $SW = 1$, $D_p = 0.25$ mm, $D_{mo} = 0.01$ m.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that intra-particle diffusion and concentration polarization are both phenomena that affect the packed bed (membrane) reactor performance for the CO₂ hydrogenation to dimethyl ether (DME), especially at conditions which are relevant to large scale operation. On the contrary, the intra-particle heat transfer, the particle–fluid mass and heat transfer as well as the axial dispersion were found to have a negligible effect on the reactor behavior.

To consider simultaneously the pore diffusion and the concentration polarization effects, a complex 3D packed bed membrane reactor (PBMR) model would be required. However, in this study, useful tools were developed to account for these phenomena using short-cut methods that can be implemented in a 1D pseudo-homogeneous reactor model.

Being the state-of-the-art Thiele modulus approach not applicable to this system, a correlation for the component-specific efficiency as a function of the Thiele modulus was developed from the simulation results of the rigorous particle model. The Thiele modulus-efficiency approach proposed here accurately predicts the CO₂ conversion and product selectivity of the rigorous particle-reactor model within a maximum deviation of 5%, for values of the Thiele modulus lower than 2.

Furthermore, to account for the concentration polarization (CP) phenomenon in a 1D PBMR model, we developed a Sherwood-type correlation for the calculation of a mass transfer coefficient (k_{CP}). The parameters of the correlation were determined fitting the simulation data obtained via the rigorous 2D PBMR model. The so-developed correlation predicts with high accuracy (i.e., deviations less than 5%) the effect of the concentration polarization on the PBMR performance.

In conclusion, given the findings of this work, both the packed bed membrane reactor (PBMR) and the packed bed reactor (PBR) could be further optimized, in view of the relevant mass/heat transfer phenomena. As an example, due to the fast methanol dehydration reaction, a considerably large fraction (i.e., up to 90%) of the zeolite in the catalytic bed could be removed with no effect on the final DME yield. Indeed, the optimal zeolite loading was found to vary in the range 4–11 wt%,

according to the catalyst particle size and the extent of water removal in the membrane reactor. Finally, in order to mitigate the impact of concentration polarization, it is possible to modify the reactor's geometry by setting a larger aspect ratio (i.e., the ratio of length to diameter), thereby increasing the superficial gas velocity.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Serena Poto: Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Huib van den Bogaard:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation. **Fausto Gallucci:** Investigation, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **M. Fernanda Neira d'Angelo:** Investigation, Supervision, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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